

Basic Human Values and Moral Foundations Theory in ValueNet Ontology

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Abstract. Values, as intended in ethics, determine the shape and validity of moral and social norms, grounding our everyday individual and community behavior on commonsense knowledge. The attempt to untangle human moral and social value-oriented structure of relations requires investigating both the dimension of subjective human perception of the world, as well as the socio-cultural dynamics and multi-agent social interactions. Formalising latent moral content in human interaction is an appealing perspective that would enable a deeper understanding of both social dynamics and individual cognitive and behavioral dimension. Nevertheless, different theoretical models include different values and organize them in different taxonomies. To formalize this broad knowledge area, in the context of ValueNet, a modular ontology representing and operationalising moral and social values, we present two modules aiming at transposing in ontological form two main theories in literature: (i) the Basic Human Values theory by Shalom Schwartz and (ii) the Moral Foundations Theory by Graham and Haidt. ValueNet is based on reusable Ontology Design Patterns, it is aligned to the DOLCE foundational ontology, and it is a component of the Framester factual-linguistic knowledge graph.

Keywords: Moral Values · Knowledge Representation · Frame Semantics · Commonsense Reasoning · Ethical AI.

1 Introduction

Values, as intended in ethics, are part of the “general frame of reference for living” [19], meaning that they are relevant (if not determinant) in our everyday behaviour and choice process, delimiting our conscious self by framing knowledge of what we *should* and what we *desire* [26], [29], [31], [23].

Bilsky and Schwartz investigating the semantics of “values” [3] conceptualize them as similar to social norms, with two important differences: (i) they are not

explicitly regulated or formalized, and (ii) their sanction-reward system operates on the emotional layer [27]. In particular they highlight five recurrent features: 1) they are considered as concepts or beliefs; 2) they are related to some desirable states or behaviours; 3) they can be deduced from their realization in specific situations but they transcend them; 4) they are pivotal for selection or evaluation processes and 5) are often organized by relative importance. The last point in particular is commonly shared among studies on the necessary scalar nature of values [36]. Being as such, they constitute a considerable hidden layer of our everyday unconscious reasoning based on commonsense knowledge in being linked to human sense-making, pattern recognition and knowledge framing abilities. Values are furthermore inextricably related to perspectivization, expression of personal positions and freedom of judgement, although the perspective of values differs from deontic reasoning since, in van Fraassen’s words [36] *deontology*, or the theory of obligations “deals with what ought to be because it is required by one’s station and its duties, by the web of obligations and commitments the past has spun”, while *axiology*, or the theory of values, “deals with what ought to be because its being so would be good, or at least better, than its alternative”. Finally, values are particularly relevant in dynamics of appraisal [33], since our choices and behaviours are typically affected by our values [26], [3]; and by the emotions arising from value-driven appraisal dynamics [25]. In social psychology, in fact, the Contempt-Anger-Disgust (CAD) triad model of moral emotions proposed by [27] relates them to specific configurations of values, termed ethics, inspired by Schweder’s work [20] on morality from an anthropological perspective. The CAD triad model relates each emotion type to the violation of a specific ethic, which motivates people to repair the moral order: Contempt to the Ethics of community, Anger to the Ethics of autonomy, Disgust to the Ethics of Divinity. These ethics can also be seen as a subset of the Moral Foundations Theory put forth by Haidt and colleagues. Finally, from a neuro-biological perspective [5], “there was a biological blueprinting for the intelligent construction of human values [...] We also believe that a variety of natural modes of biological responses, which include those known as emotions, already embody such values.”. Therefore, the attempt to formalize the complex structure of relations of moral and social values requires investigating the domain of subjective human perception as well as socio-cultural dynamics, in order to formalize the elusive nature of values as “abstract objects with social capital” [14].

The paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 we provide an overview of the resources reused and already existing material, in particular Section 2.1 introduces the frame semantics approach adopted to model the whole ValueNet modular ontology, which is described in Section 2.2, in particular ValueCore and MFTriggers modules are introduced in Sections 2.3 and 2.4. Section 3 explains in detail the new ontological modules introduced in ValueNet in order to formalize the existing theoretical background, in particular Section 3.1 is focused on Basic Human Values theory, while section 3.2 is focused on Moral Foundations Theory. Finally, Section 4 provides some testing of the ontological modules introduced,

while Section 4.3 envisions further operationalization and maintenance of the resource.

This work started being developed originally in the SPICE project context, mentioned in Section 5 and available on GitHub⁴.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we give an overview of ValueNet, we introduce the ontological modules about moral and social value theories, then we provide an overview of the theoretical background, in particular the Basic Human Values theory [29] and the Moral Foundations Theory [15], formalised with a frame semantics [8] approach (cf. Section 2.2).

2.1 Frame Semantics and Framester

The approach adopted to model ValueNet, and to connect it to the linguistic expression of values, reuses a formal representation of FrameNet frames [7] as formalised [24] in Framester [9]. Frames are defined as cognitive representations of prototypical and recurrent features of events or situations. Lexical units semantically related to some scene are associated with frames, based on their schematic structure. In FrameNet, frames are also explained as *situation types*. In Framester semantics [8] observed/recalled/anticipated/imagined situations are consequently occurrences of frames. For example, representing an apparently simple situation like the moral emotion [35] “feeling ashamed” as a frame structure, it would require some *necessary roles* such as an agent feeling the emotion (experiencer), the emotion itself, but also some optional elements such as an emotion trigger, the intensity, the physiological manifestation, and some external elements such as the duration of the emotion feeling / state. Therefore, frame semantics assumes that frames provide a coherent schematization of experience. Thus, widely acknowledged frames provide a theoretically well founded, and a practically validated basis, for commonsense knowledge patterns.

Framester [9] provides a formal semantics for frames in a curated linked data version of multiple linguistic resources (e.g. besides FrameNet, WordNet [21], VerbNet [28], BabelNet [22], etc.); a cognitive layer including MetaNet [10] and ImageSchemaNet [6], connecting conceptual metaphors and image schematic sensorimotor patterns to the above-mentioned linguistic resources; factual knowledge bases (e.g. DBpedia [2], YAGO [34], etc.), and ontology schemas (e.g. DOLCE [11]), with formal links between them, resulting in a strongly connected RDF/OWL knowledge graph.

Framester can be used to jointly query (via a SPARQL endpoint⁵) the resources aligned to its formal frame ontology⁶.

⁴ The SPICE GitHub is available here: <https://github.com/spice-h2020/SON>

⁵ Framester SPARQL endpoint is available at: <http://etna.istc.cnr.it/framester2/sparql>

⁶ Framester Schema is available at: <https://w3id.org/framester/schema/>

2.2 ValueNet

Fig. 1. ValueNet import and usage network.

ValueNet⁷ modular ontology is an extension of Framester, therefore values are modeled as framal structures triggered by many other Framester entities. Its purpose is twofold: (i) on one hand, it aims at formalizing existing theories about moral and social values, with the goal to create a formal integrated environment, based on the general ValueCore module⁸, explained in section 2.3, which allows the integration of theoretical knowledge with experimental data based on a certain theory; on the other hand (ii) it aims at operationalizing existing theories developing sense-making tools, e.g., the value detector based on MFT as explained in Section 2.4.

2.3 ValueCore

The ValueCore module models the notion of “value” as a frame. It reuses the Description&Situation ontology design pattern [12], considering each value of

⁷ ValueNet repository is available here: <https://github.com/StenDoipanni/ValueNet>

⁸ The ValueCore graph is available here:

<https://github.com/StenDoipanni/ValueNet/blob/main/ValueCore.ttl>

each theory (formalized in a separate module, here we present the Basic Human Values and the Moral Foundations Theory, but Section 4.3 envisions further extensions) as a `fschema:ConceptualFrame`, subclass of `dul:Description`, satisfied by some `vc:ValueSituation`, namely, the realization / occurrence of some prototypical type of event involving some value. In particular, the ValueCore module includes three main types of value-driven situations according to state of the art literature: (i) `vc:ValueAppraisal`: the appraisal of a situation performed by an agent, pivoted by a value; (ii) `vc:ValueCommitment`: the commitment of an agent to a value; and (iii) `vc:ValueRecognition`: the recognition, namely, the plane existence assertion, operated by some agent, of a value in some context. These three types of situation, modeled as framal structures including necessary, optional and external roles allow to model each and any type of event including some value, with an increasing degree of formal complexity proportional to the granularity of desired specificity in describing the scenario taken in consideration⁹.

The ValueCore module furthermore allows to perform queries about a single instance of some value, according to one or many theories, and perform useful inferences about classes modeled in each different module. Useful queries about modules described in Sections 3.1 and 3.2 are listed in Section 4, and provided as support material on the ValueNet GitHub.

Furthermore, the whole ValueCore module can be explored online via the Framester endpoint¹⁰.

2.4 MFTriggers

Another module included in ValueNet is MFTriggers. MFTriggers intends to fill a gap: there is no repository that provides alignments for entities from different semantic layers (lexical units, semantic roles, framal structures, factual entities, etc.), to a social or moral value from any theory. Albeit the Extended Moral Foundations Dictionary [18] has been extensively used to train neural models with the task of detecting moral values, no direct lexical grounding has been provided for any of the elements of the Graham and Haidt’s dyadic oppositions, let alone as semantic web resources.

In order to operationalise ValueNet and fill that gap, MFTriggers introduces a lexical and factual grounding, using a *heuristic abstraction* method. For example considering the set of lexical units evoking the `mft:Harm` frame, namely, the broad notion of “harm” according to the Moral Foundations Theory, this set includes WordNet synsets such as `wn:killer-noun-1`, `wn:harm-verb-1`, `wn:wound-noun-1` and many others. Therefore, considering a sentence like “someone has to stop that awful killer”, after performing a disambiguation and retrieving that the lexical unit “killer” is disambiguated on the `wn:killer-noun-1` synset, by heuristic inference we can say that in the above mentioned sentence there is an occurrence of a `mft:Harm` situation.

⁹ The ValueCore module is available here:

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/StenDoipanni/ValueNet/main/ValueCore.ttl>

¹⁰ The Framester endpoint is available here: <http://etna.istc.cnr.it/framester2/sparql>

Since the Framester knowledge graph implements a formal frame semantics in OWL2, it is appropriate to heuristic abstraction by creating interoperability across existing lexical and factual resources, re-engineered (or directly reused) as knowledge graphs, and aligned to frames and foundational ontologies. A graph-based value detector has been developed applying this heuristic and it is mentioned in Section 4.

3 ValueNet Theoretical Modules

The following sections introduce the BHV and MFT ontological modules, namely the transposition of the Basic Human Values theory and the Moral Foundations Theory in ontological form, showing their main focus and possible inferences. BHV and MFT as theories share some overlaps but starts from quite different perspectives, greatly simplified: both theories propose a “universal” model, namely a model which should provide a cultural-agnostic explanation for the whole human value system, and for this reason are modeled in ValueNet. But while MFT adopts a more developmental perspective (explained in detail in Section 3.2), BHV considers many socio-behavioral factors. This difference results in both theories having a relational “opposition” of values but while MFT is organized in dyadic oppositions of one value and its violation, BHV circumplex model does not contemplate direct violations, but rather opposition of behavioral focus and attitude. Being the ontological transposition of theories BHV and MFT should be able to represent the pivotal theoretical assumptions in the theory of reference, plus some theory-dependent inference in a plausible scenario.

3.1 Basic Human Values

The Theory of Basic Human Values (BHV) by Shalom Schwartz was proposed as a pan-cultural theory in the 1980s. Its main assumption is that human values are organized in a “value wheel”, that is, an ordering structure that organizes values as a circumplex model, dividing them in four quadrants with two opposing axes, and a congruity continuum between adjacent values.

Originally, the model included 10 values [29], but, as shown in fig. 3.1, the model was later refined to 19 values in total [31]. BHV relies on the opposition and similarity of values, grouped into macro-categories that are mostly determined by individual personality traits (self-transcendence vs self-enhancement, conservation vs openness to change). This model has inspired the design of a questionnaire (Portrait Values Questionnaire, PTV) which has been employed by a number of studies to explore values across different countries [32]. In recent work [30], Schwartz provides evidence in favour of a pan-cultural arrangement of value priorities.

BHV has been tested on a vast number of subjects across 82 countries. However, one of the main criticism is its top-down approach, establishing the number and taxonomy of values a-priori, and then validating it through dedicated experimentation.

Fig. 2. Basic Human Values circumplex model, image taken from [Giménez, August Corrons, and Lluís Garay Tamajón. "Analysis of the third-order structuring of Shalom Schwartz's theory of basic human values." *Heliyon* 5.6 (2019): e01797.]

BHV Classes The ontology takes as source the BHV model reworked as in [13]. It is the attempt to formalize values as an *inner behavioral nudge*, related to outer stimula, towards one (or more) of the four main axes as explained in the following.

The ontology includes two top classes representing the “attitude”, i.e., a general view of the world, driving some more specific ordering principles; four classes representing a “focus”, i.e., a taxonomical criterion that addresses the entities (social group, individual, society, class) supposed to profit the most from some value; 4 third order clusters of values, which split the circumplex model in four quadrants, creating diagonal opposition and topical continuity; 12 second order values, namely more specific clusters of values considering a more fine-grained granularity in framing events and situations of the world; and finally 19 first order values, which explicitly state the patient / beneficiary of some value. We list here the ontological classes and axioms, from the most general ones (which in the circumplex model corresponds to most external sectors), to the most specific.

The highest order layer of the circumplex model is formalized as follows:

- `bhv:GrowthAndAnxietyFree` : This is a pro-active attitude, characterizing a self-transcendent view of the world and a higher openness to novelty and change.
- `bhv:SelfProtectionAndAnxietyAvoidance` : this is a more reactive attitude, characterizes as a self-centered view of the world fostering a closer and conservative attitude.

Moving one ring inward into the circumplex model, the “focus” concept is modeled as follows:

- **bhv:SocialFocus** : Focus on social issues and others than self, or focus on self, considered as a member of a social community. The focus expresses the main beneficiary of the behaviour determined by some Value e.g. the class **SelfTranscendence** is the superclass grouping all the Values having as focus society more than the individual;
- **bhv:PersonalFocus** : Focus on personal issues and self, both as realization of self intended as freedom of thinking and action as well as dominance over others.

The third order values structuring the four main quadrants of the circumplex model are formalized considering diagonal oppositions, and some axiomatization according to their focus and attitude:

- **bhv:Conservation** : This macro category is focused on “preserving stability and security”, in particular “with the emphasis on subservient self-repression, the preservation of traditional practices and protecting stability”. In the BHV ontological module its attitude and focus are axiomatised as:

$$\begin{aligned} & ((\text{focus some PersonalFocus}) \text{ or } (\text{focus some SocialFocus})) \\ & \quad \text{and } (\text{attitude only SelfProtectionAndAnxietyAvoidance}) \quad (1) \\ & \quad \quad \text{and } (\text{valueMotivation only Conservation}) \end{aligned}$$

Its opposite quadrant is:

- **bhv:OpennessToChange** : it consists in readiness for new experience, self centered values which foster physical and intellectual freedom and fulfillment. Its focus and attitude are formalized as:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\text{attitude only GrowthAndAnxietyFree}) \text{ and} \\ & \quad (\text{focus only PersonalFocus}) \text{ and} \quad (2) \\ & \quad (\text{valueMotivation only OpennessToChange}) \end{aligned}$$

According to the **bhv:PersonalFocus** dimension, the sibling class to **OpennessToChange** in the circumplex model is:

- **bhv:SelfEnhancement** : it consists in promoting self-interest, often at the expense of others, emphasising the search for personal success and dominance over others. Its focus and attitude are formalized as:

$$\begin{aligned} & ((\text{attitude some GrowthAndAnxietyFree}) \text{ or} \\ & (\text{attitude some SelfProtectionAndAnxietyAvoidance})) \text{ and} \quad (3) \\ & \quad (\text{focus only PersonalFocus}) \text{ and} \\ & \quad (\text{valueMotivation only SelfEnhancement}) \end{aligned}$$

In the opposed quadrant to **bhv:Self-Enhancement** there is:

- **bhv:SelfTranscendence** : it consists in promoting the well-being of society and nature above one’s own interests, highlighting the acceptance of others as equals, as well as a concern for their well-being. Its focus and attitude are formalized as:

$$\begin{aligned} &(\text{attitude only GrowthAndAnxietyFree}) \text{ and} \\ &(\text{focus only SocialFocus}) \text{ and} \\ &(\text{valueMotivation only SelfTranscendence}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the full list of 19 first order BHV values is shown in figure 3.1 and each value class is described in the OWL file¹¹.

BHV Object Properties The object properties modeled in BHV module are:

- **bhv:attitude** : this property is used to declare the attitude corresponding to some values, namely **sch:SelfProtectionAndAnxietyAvoidance** (re-active attitude) vs **bhv:GrothAndAnxietyFree** (pro-active attitude).
- **bhv:focus** : this property is used to declare the focus corresponding to some values, namely **bhv:SocialFocus** vs **bhv:PersonalFocus**.
- **bhv:opposingFocus** : serves the function of modelling oppositions, as described in previous paragraphs and figure 3.1.
- **bhv:opposingValueMotivation** : Following the polarity opposition Conservation vs OpennesToChange and SelfTranscendence vs SelfEnhancement, this property is used to declare e.g. that one value having as valueMotivation (see below) Conservation has as opposingValueMotivation OpennesToChange.
- **bhv:panCulturallyMoreImportantThat** : to express the eventuality of building a Pan Cultural Baseline For Values Priority.
- **bhv:valueMotivation** : This property links all the values to their Value Motivation, namely **bhv:Conservation** or **bhv:SelfEnhancement** or **bhv:OpennessToChange** or **bhv:SelfTranscendence**. It is also used in the axiomatization to define the intensionality of each of the mentioned classes using this property to declare them as having as motivation themselves. For example, a **bhv:SelfTranscendence** occurrence, namely, an extensional realization of **bhv:SelfTranscendence**, which in the real world could be e.g. an act of generosity, has as value motivation, namely, could be ascribed to some macro-category, the intensional concept of **bhv:SelfTranscendence**.

BHV Competency Questions BHV module allows to answer some CQs according to BHV theory, such as:

1. Is the entity x an instance of some value, according to BHV theory?
2. What values have as focus some **bhv:SocialFocus** or **bhv:PersonalFocus**?
3. What is the **bhv:opposingFocus** of some value?
4. What is the attitude of some value?
5. What is the value motivation for some value?

¹¹ The ontology is available here: <https://github.com/spice-h2020/SON/blob/main/SchwartzValues/ontology.owl>

3.2 Moral Foundations Theory

The Moral Foundation Theory (MFT) is proposed as a cultural-independent theory of moral and social values, inspired by Schweder's et al. work on universal human ethics [20] and tightly related to the investigation of moral emotions, with a particular focus on behavioural neuro-cognitivism. Its agnostic point of view towards cultural dependencies is realized via its dyadic oppositional structure. On one hand, the intension of dyadic oppositions is supposed to be cultural independent; on the other hand, their extension is dependent on the actual realization of one (or more) dyadic value in some situation of the real world. The model proposed by [16] focuses mainly on single value oppositions, where any pair of opposing values represents the poles of a prescribing/inhibiting dyad. MFT describes six innate moral foundations across cultures and societies:

- Care vs Harm is grounded in the attachment systems and some form of empathy, intended as the ability to not only understand, but also feel, the same feelings as others, thus being able to imagine hypothetical scenarios, in which we are living some positive or negative mental or physical state, which we actually don't live.
- Fairness vs Cheating is grounded in the evolutionary process of reciprocal altruism.
- Loyalty vs Betrayal is grounded in the clans and family-based dimension that for a long time characterized most of our tribal societies. The ability to create links and alliances was a way to increase the surviving percentage possibilities for oneself and his/her close group.
- Authority vs Subversion is grounded in the hierarchical social interactions directly inherited by primates' societies.
- Sanctity vs Degradation is grounded in the CAD triad emotions (Contempt, Anger, Disgust) and the psychology of disgust, it is one of the most spread dyadic oppositions, being foundational for the opposition between soul and flesh.
- Liberty vs Oppression is grounded in feelings and experiences like solidarity, vs. episodes of unjustified violence or liberty restrictions.

Besides its relevance for the investigation of the emotional counterpart of value appraisal and for the cross-cultural investigation of values, MFT has inspired the design of the Moral Foundation Dictionary [17] and, more recently, of the Extended Moral Foundations Dictionary [18], which combine theory-driven elements on moral intuitions with a data-oriented approach. Relationship with the emotion knowledge layer is envisioned as future work in Section 4.3.

Factual situations can evoke some Value, and be opposed by some Violation, creating multi-shaped scenarios, in which the same Event or Action or Entity can evoke different Values and their Violations at the same time.

MFT Classes The MFT module is light-weighted considering the number of axioms, due to the fact that the whole theory is based on direct dyadic opposition of values and violations. MFT classes are:

- `mft:DyadicOpposition` : this is the superclass for all the value-violation dyads. It `dul:hasComponent` exactly 1 value and exactly 1 violation.
- `mft:Value` : this is the class for “positive” values shaping some behavior, it is subclass of `vc:Value` in the ValueCore module.
- `mft:Violation` : this class represent the violation to some value, they can also be conceived as “negative” values.

MFT Object Properties The object properties modeled in MFT module are:

- `mft:opposedTo` : some value is opposed to its violation in the dyadic structure. This property is symmetric.
- `mft:violates` : some violation violates some `dul:Norm`.
- `dul:hasComponent` : this property expresses the mereological aspect of some dyad.

MFT Competency Questions MFT module allows to answer some CQs according to MFT theory, such as:

1. Is the entity x an instance of some value, according to MFT theory?
2. What is the value `mft:opposedTo` some entity x ?

And thanks to the MFTriggers modules and the value detection tool described in Section 4:

1. Is there some value in the sentence y ?
2. What is the value profile of (namely the set of values activated by) some word or sentence?

4 Evaluation: BHV and MFT Operationalization

BHV and MFT describe primitive framing of values as descriptions, and are typically associable to real world occurrences (situations), named `vc:ValueSituation`. A value situation presents elements coherent to the conceptualization of BHV or MFT, so that it can answer competency questions mentioned in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

To allow an evaluation of the ontological module we propose here a scenario answering CQs mentioned in Section 3.1 and 3.2, involving at the same time three types of value situations according to ValueCore module, namely `vc:ValueRecognition`, `vc:ValueAppraisal` and `vc:ValueCommitment`.

Value Scenario UserA and UserB are visiting an art gallery and see a painting depicting Pietro Micca (“Pietro Micca nel punto di dare fuoco alla mina volge a Dio e alla Patria I suoi ultimi pensieri” - “Pietro Micca, the moment before setting fire to the bomb, directs his thoughts to God and his motherland”) by Andrea Gastaldi. Pietro Micca is described as an Italian patriot who gave his

life to save the to-be-born state of Italy, igniting some dynamite to detonate a tunnel that was being invaded by enemy soldiers.

Pietro Micca’s action can be modeled as a `vc:ValueCommitment` situation, nested in two different interpretations of UserA and UserB which can be modeled as `vc:ValueRecognition` situations, and for each of them would be possible to express the appraisal and the desirability of some action for both Users in a `vc:ValueAppraisal` situation¹²

4.1 BHV Evaluation

UserA declares to be proud of the action made by Pietro Micca, sharing with him the value “Patriotism”. UserB disagrees considering more important “Self Preservation” than sacrificing one’s own life for the country. Thanks to BHV module and the lexical tokens linked to the first order values, “Patriotism” is inferred as being an instance of the `bhv:Societal`, situated in the `bhv:Conservation` quadrant, while “Self-Preservation” is an instance of `bhv:Action`, situated in the `bhv:OpennessToChange` quadrant.

We can infer that UserA’s instance of “Patriotism” has `bhv:focus` some `bhv:SocialFocus` and attitude some `bhv:SelfProtectionAndAnxietyAvoidance`; while for UserB’s value instance we can infer that it has some `bhv:PersonalFocus` and `bhv:GrowthAndAnxietyFree` attitude.

The scenario proposed here in natural language is available serialized in turtle syntax both on the ValueNet and SPICE project GitHub. Finally, knowledge graphs of semantic triggers operationalizing BHV theory providing an automatic extraction of value situations and value detector from natural language (as for MFT, in MFTriggers graphs described in Section 4.2) are being developed and are mentioned as future work in section 4.3.

4.2 MFT Evaluation

UserA declare to be proud of the Action made by Pietro Micca, focusing on the result of this action, namely the Liberty of Italy. UserB disagrees, considering more important Pietro Micca’s life than any victory in war, in fact she/he considers it useless to sacrifice oneself for any country. Thanks to the MFT dyadic model, “LibertyOfItaly” is inferred as being an instance of `mft:Liberty`, while “CareOfPietroMicca” is an instance of `mft:Care`, and “PietroMiccaSacrifice” is an instance of `mft:Harm`.

Other than this ontological representation capability, as mentioned in Sections 2.4 and 3.2, the MFTriggers ontology module operationalizes the Moral

¹² We do not provide details about the ValueCore possible inferences here since it’s not the main focus, but further details are available on the ValueNet GitHub: <https://github.com/StenDoipanni/ValueNet> and on the SPICE project GitHub: https://github.com/spice-h2020/SON/blob/main/SchwartzValues/Schwartz_scenario.ttl

Foundations Theory. As evaluation, we point at the results of a value detection frame-structured and graph-based model tested on a large natural language corpus [1].

4.3 Conclusions and Future Improvement

We presented here the BHV and MFT theoretical modules integrated in the ValueNet ontology. The ontology is an ongoing attempt to formalize different perspectivizations depending on the cognitive framing that agents make in relation to some stimulus. The ValueNet repository is constantly updated and improved with the introduction of formal axioms from new theories and new triggers from different resources. The current version includes the ValueCore and MFTriggers modules, as well as the newly introduced and presented here BHV and MFT ontologies.

Future developments on the theoretical side include the introduction of new theoretical modules, such as Curry’s “Moral Molecules” [4] theory¹³; while on the operational side they include the semantic triggers knowledge graphs generation, starting from resources like Schwartz’s Portrait Value Questionnaire [30]. On a parallel research direction ontological modules formalizing theoretical Emotion theories and generating semantic triggers knowledge graphs are being developed and introduced as an Emotion knowledge layer in the Framester resource. Future developments will be to conjugate these two intertwined layers in more complex formal semantics representations.

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A Ontology Prefixes

DOLCE foundational ontology:

dul : <<http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/dul/DUL.owl/>>

Framester schema

fschema : <<https://w3id.org/framester/schema/>>

MFT module:

mft : <<https://w3id.org/spice/SON/HaidtValues#>>

BHV module:

bhv : <<https://w3id.org/spice/SON/SchwartzValues#>>

ValueCore module :

vc : <<http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/values/valuecore.owl#>>

¹³ Curry’s ontological module is available at:

<https://github.com/StenDoipanni/ValueNet/tree/main/MoralMolecules>

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